

FAMILY IS THE BEST SUPPORT OF OUR SOCIETY

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Annotation: This article describes the views of the President on the family, the sanctity of the family, family relations, the role of the family in society.

Keywords: Family, marriage, respect, honor, humanity, livelihood, supreme blessing.

A family is a small group based on marriage or birth. Its members are bound by the unity of life values, mutual assistance and moral responsibility. The most important social tasks of the family are the continuation of the human race, the upbringing of children, the effective organization of the life and free time of family members. Although family relations are considered a relatively independent phenomenon, they are determined by social, economic and worldview relations existing in society and change under their influence. Accordingly, each society changes and establishes the appropriate type of family, family relations. The family did not exist in the history of society. At the first stage of the primitive communal system, when people lived in groups, relations between the sexes did not have a definite order, and all men and women in the group were considered common spouses. However, these families do not yet have a stable separate household. public production. With the development of animal husbandry and agriculture, the cost of men's labor increased, their share in production increased, and, consequently, their social status changed radically.

The existing rules and regulations - that children belong only to the mother, that they are considered heirs of the mother's property - contradicted the new status of a man. As a result, a patriarchal family was created, based on the rights of the father. The family checks the traditions of life and marriage of the people and society. He carefully preserves the good ones and passes them on to future generations. The family educates their children and instills in them universal human values, giving them an initial socio-economic orientation. By adding a few children to the broader stream of society, the family has little influence in determining the direction, economy, culture, and education of society. That is why the family has long been considered a sacred fortress in the East. In particular, features of Uzbek families are still preserved. For Uzbeks, elderly people and parents play a big role in shaping a certain family lifestyle, gaining life experience, a thrifty and healthy lifestyle, and raising children to be polite and spiritually mature. Uzbek families are distinguished by their strength, organization, childhood, respect for family ties, goodwill and other values.

Thanks to the state independence of Uzbekistan, the ancient national traditions and rituals of our people began to be restored, these traditions play an important role in strengthening the family. The Government of Uzbekistan considers family issues as a priority task that must be addressed at the level of state policy. According to Article 63 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the family is the main link in society, it has the

right to be protected by society and the state. Other legal documents on the protection of motherhood and childhood have been adopted and practical measures have been identified. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan declared 1998 the "Year of the Family" in order to further enhance the role and participation of the family in the development of society, strengthen state support and consistently improve the legal, social, economic, moral and moral interests and well-being of the family. Based on this, a state program was developed on measures to ensure the interests of the family. The Scientific and Practical Center "Family" of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established under the Women's Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dedicated to the legal regulation of family life issues, was adopted. Happy families make a happy society. Because happy parents raise happy children. Children of parents who love each other will also love each other.

The family is a sacred place that preserves the continuity of every people and nation, ensures the development of national values, gives birth to a new generation, educates them spiritually and physically, and is considered the main foundation of society. The family is one of the most beautiful wonders of nature, and it is for people. This is a social unit based on special "natural-biological", economic, legal and spiritual relations. The family is the most important part of people's lives, the basis of civil society. In this holy place, a person is born, and it is here that he matures spiritually and morally.

For the emergence and dominance of love in the family, the following conditions are expected:

- mutual respect of family members;
- family members trust and protect each other;
- closeness, mutual support and exchange of thoughts;
- sense of responsibility (parents' sense of their duties and responsibilities);
- to face difficulties together and solve them;
- be able to express their identity and create a suitable environment for a happy life;
- have a healthy material and spiritual life;

Nowadays, we should also give similar advice, especially to our young brides and grooms, we should perfectly explain halal and haram, marital duties, especially matters that lead to the breakdown of marriage. Then every family will live a strong, peaceful, peaceful and happy life. Divorces can be avoided due to some minor flaws and misunderstandings. Family happiness is considered a great blessing. In this sense, it is necessary to pay attention to the relationship between husband and wife, mother-in-law and daughter-in-law, parents and children in the happiness and peace of family life. In order to create a high spiritual atmosphere in the family environment, family members, especially husband and wife, should compromise with each other, overcome their anger when it comes, and be sweet-spoken, at the same time, they should not reveal family secrets to the street. A number of factors are of great importance.

Recently, our country has introduced a medical examination of the bride and groom before marriage, taking into account the stability of the family, the happiness of the bride and groom, and the health of future offspring. Parents who have carefully raised their daughter in a marriage with great hopes and great expense, and who dream of having grandchildren who have a son-in-law through their daughter, soon after the marriage will find out that their son-in-law has an incurable disease, think about it. Or if your son-in-law turns out to be a drug addict, and your daughter is happy, the world will become narrower in your eyes.

Living, working and raising children honestly in family relationships, which have received little recognition over the centuries and have risen to the level of religious and moral values, are the source of the development of social life. In Eastern education, the basis for the formation of a universal worldview of a person begins with the family. That is, all the factors that determine the meaning of human life, such as patriotism, kindness, manners and honesty, are formed in the family. The role of the family in the development of every small child into an adult is very important. Every parent wants his child to grow up worthy of his country and take his place in life. Every young person who has reached the age of majority and has created a family must be mentally and physically ready to start a family. The Uzbek folk writer Fitrat said about the family: The happiness and dignity of each family depends on the internal discipline and consent of this people. And peace and harmony depend on the discipline of national families, and the country and peoples will also become stronger. If the population of a country, by immorality and ignorance, weakens family relations and allows indiscipline, then the happiness and life of this nation will be in question.

A healthy child is born directly from a successful marriage and a close-knit family. The fact that this year has been declared by our state as the “Year of a Healthy Child” is another practical expression of the attention and care shown to the health of our children and their future. The future of a country with healthy children will be bright and its goals will be clear. In his speeches, the head of our state showed how important the role of the family is in the health and well-being of the child, and said: “It takes a lot to give birth to a healthy child growing strong, which we all understand. that it depends on factors. But among them there are such extremely important, decisive criteria that I consider it appropriate to dwell on them separately. We accept it as a place of education that shows mystery. Noble qualities such as respect for elders, respect for children, humanity, kindness, loyalty to the Motherland and people are formed in a family environment. That is why the family is a comprehensively developed and healthy generation. Its significance in bringing to adulthood is incomparable,” they emphasize.

In this article, several views are put forward on the personal activity of a gifted child, as well as the formation and implementation of individual talent on the basis of which the psychological mechanisms of self-development of the lying person are important.

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.

Uzbekistan has a rich experience of political life, features of political consciousness and develops in unique and difficult conditions. Thus, it turned out that it is wrong to copy a simple copy of the political experience of the Western world.

Conclusion: The main task of the family is to educate perfect people devoted to society. After all, a healthy child is the fruit of a healthy family. When we say a healthy person, we understand not only physical health, but also a mature person who has matured in the spirit of oriental customs, national ideals and noble feelings, such as tolerance and humanism characteristic of the Uzbek people. After all, spiritually healthy people can, first of all, take care of the peace of the country, the well-being of the people, and the future of the people. We can say that the source of support is a healthy family environment, a healthy ideology and a spiritually healthy person. The family, which is a strong pillar of our society, not only

educates people of tomorrow, but is also able to form the ability to take care of the Motherland and tomorrow.

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